

NUMERICAL MODELING OF RESIN SHRINKAGE AROUND INSERT IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH PANELS

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a numerical approach to characterize the formation of local deformations appearing on the visible side of composite sandwich panels used for interior furniture of business airplanes. The proposed parametric model based on finite elements finds its complexity into the meso-scale mechanic and an accurate modelling of resin properties evolution through curing. Pre-processing and finite elements computing are performed with ABAQUS in an uncoupled thermo-mechanical analysis. The model showed that the geometry of the constituents and their thermo-mechanical properties such as resin shrinkage may have an influence. Possible improvements to the model to better reproduce the reality are discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures have become inevitable in the aeronautic and automotive industry where combining lightness, high rigidity and strength is essential. Baseline composite sandwich panels are often modified for specific applications. Once covered with a thin fine wood laminate, the panels become the main components of many interior furniture of business airplanes. For an assembly purpose, polymeric or metallic inserts can be inserted within the core. Metallic inserts are generally bonded with an epoxy resin within a blind hole drilled in the sandwich core. Unfortunately, the presence of the inserts leads to surface defects appearing on the visible side of the panel. The crater-like deformations of less than a millimetre in depth are clearly visible by the human eye. Moreover, they can appear months after the airplane delivery causing costly reparations.

The appearance of those local deformations can be caused by resin shrinkage, mechanical loading or a combination of both. Resin shrinkage [1] and mechanic of composite sandwich [2-4] are intensively investigated in the literature. However, to the best knowledge of the authors, research focusing on the analysis of the formation of the local defect due to the chemical shrinkage in the insert region of the sandwich panel is rare [5, 6, 7].

The objective of the present study is to investigate the physical phenomena leading to the formation of such local defects. The problem finds its complexity into the coupled effect of chemical, thermal and mechanical phenomena. The small scale of the studied defects also urges to analyse each constitutive elements (honeycomb, face sheet, resin and metallic inserts) and their interactions adequately. A parametric numerical model is proposed to predict the formation of the local deformations given the thermo-mechanical properties of the resin and other elements of the assembly. A typical assembly is schematised in Figure 1.

Figure 1 : Sandwich panel constituents

2 NUMERICAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Simulation approach

In order to simplify the computing method, the thermal and mechanical analyses were separated. The exothermal and curing phenomena driven by the resin chemical reaction were simulated regardless of mechanics for the complete sequence. Then, the temperature and degree of cure for every time steps were transferred as predefined field into the mechanical analysis steps. Those fields are the source of all displacements observed during the mechanical analysis. No external loads were applied to the assembly. Thermal fields create thermal expansion while degree of cure influences resin mechanical properties and chemical shrinkage. The coupling is not necessary because stress and displacement have no effects on the heat transfer analysis. Displacements are small and can therefore be neglected. Figure 2 clarifies the simulation procedure.

Figure 2 : Overview of the simulation approach

2.2 Model overview

In order to assess the influence of every constituent, a finite element model was proposed. The model has to be well detailed considering the scale of the defects and the region analysed. Skins and honeycomb walls were modelled with shell elements. The resin and the insert were modelled with solid elements and merged together producing a perfect cohesion since they share the same boundary nodes. The bonding interaction of the resin region with the honeycomb and the skins were made of tie constraints, linking all nodes' degrees of freedom (DOF). The glued joint of the honeycomb cell walls was not considered. A double thickness wall was used instead.

Figure 3 : (a) Numerical model geometry and (b) Mesh of a deformed shape (50x)

The epoxy resin and metallic insert are considered isotropic. The skin, fabricated with quasi-isotropic fiberglass panels is also considered isotropic. The honeycomb has orthotropic properties based on literature [8, 9]. Mechanical analyses are linear, no buckling is considered. This assumption is motivated by the small size of the local deformations. The mechanical boundary conditions are minimal and limit free body motion only. The heat transfer analysis considers only conduction in the part and convection boundary conditions on both skins.

Examples of an undeformed and deformed area are shown on Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b), respectively. The deformed skin (red) and the metallic insert (grey) can be clearly seen. To reduce the processing time and simplify the numerical analysis, only one quarter of the deformed region was modelled. However, due to the hexagonal geometry of the honeycomb, only a few hole positions in the honeycomb leads to a truly symmetric model. Full panels were simulated to verify the effect of the hole position relative to the honeycomb structure. This analysis was carried out to make sure that the output of the model (local deformations) does not depend on the hole position. A convergence analysis on the mesh element size was also conducted to evaluate the numerical error contribution.

The creation of the geometry and the finite element analysis was conducted with ABAQUS. Most of the operations were performed with ABAQUS to keep the numeric tool easy to use and share. ABAQUS can be controlled with Python script where every parameter of interests is associated with variables. It is also possible to run multiple analyses through loops and automate the post-processing.

2.3 Subroutines

ABAQUS Subroutines were used to describe the resin behaviour.

The heat generation subroutine **HETVAL** allows the resin mesh elements to release heat during the thermal analysis. The heat released being closely linked with resin curing, the subroutine handle the degree of cure within the elements. A cure kinetics model establishes the link between heat and curing. This model is based on differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) experiments performed on resin samples.

Resin shrinkage during the mechanical analysis is managed by an **UEXPAN** subroutine. The subroutine also handles the thermal expansion. Both contributions are combined in one expansion value. The subroutine receives as input the degree of cure and the temperature. The shrinkage values and thermal expansion coefficient are obtained from experiments and are measured in the glassy and rubbery states of the resin.

As the resin cures, mechanical properties evolve. Thus, the resin goes from an almost liquid state to its final solidified state. The **UMAT** subroutine receives the degree of cure and temperature of every

element to calculate its new Young Modulus. A function interpolates the value between the rubbery and glassy state modulus. Those mechanical properties are obtained from experimental dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). The Young modulus is also used to calculate the shear modulus from Poisson's ratio. Thereafter, the Jacobian stiffness matrix is updated and used to calculate stress increment from strain increment. That way, an element stretched with low force while in the liquid phase will not force its way back in its initial position during the transition to a more rigid and solid phase.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Numerical simulation

Sensibility analyzes are carried out on the insert length and also on skin, honeycomb and resin rigidity. Resin shrinkage and cavity radius are also evaluated by a score given to the defects. Only the visible surface is considered to evaluate the score, this surface corresponds to the red surface of Figure 3(b). The score is based on the numerical integration of the depth of the surface to square. This method is similar to calculating the volume of the crater, but will penalize deeper defects that are easily seen by human eye. Figure 4 displays standardized scoring, based on hypothetical spherical defects of 15 mm of diameter and of different depth. Only a quarter of the defect is represented on a square region of 25 mm sides. A flat plate would have a score of zero, whereas higher score corresponds to more deformed area.

Figure 4 : Standardized scoring

Every sensibility analysis has, displayed in blue⊗, the nominal configuration used as base. It has a score of 1.90 and its deformed surface is presented in Figure 5. The scale of the score ranges from 0 to 4 for every analysis in order to ease the comparisons.

Figure 5 : Deformation of the nominal configuration

Figure 6 shows the numerical prediction of the insert length influence on the defect severity. The insert length displayed on the abscissa are relative to the panel thickness. Thereby, longer insert with a relative length closer to 1 offer better results. One of the longest insert is kept as the nominal configurations for the subsequent sensibility analyzes in this article.

Figure 6 : Influence of insert length

Effects of the rigidity of the skins, honeycomb and resins are examined through 6 simulations where the parameter of interest is varied from half the nominal property to its double. Curing characteristics of the resin such as volumetric shrinkage are explored on a realistic scope of values. The influence of the radius of the honeycomb cavity is also simulated. The effect of the rigidity of the skin is observed by varying the thickness (Figure 7(a)) and the modulus (Figure 7(b)). The same approach is used for the mechanical properties of the honeycomb on Figure 8. Those figures demonstrate that skin rigidity has almost no effect while an increase in honeycomb rigidity significantly reduces the score. However, the honeycomb effect does not seem linear as it has a tendency to stabilize for higher rigidity.

Figure 7 : Influence of skin: (a) thickness and (b) modulus

Figure 8 : Influence of honeycomb: (a) wall thickness and (b) modulus

Figure 9 : Influence of resin: (a) modulus and (b) resin volumetric shrinkage

The resin modulus has an opposite behavior to honeycomb rigidity. Both have a nonlinear effect lessening at higher modulus, but resin increases the defect while honeycomb reduces it. Volumetric shrinkage exhibits a strong effect on defect score. This result was anticipated since the shrinkage is expected to contribute the most to variation of dimensions of polymer matrix composite parts.

The influence of the radius of the cavity in Figure 10 indicates that higher radius clearly leads to larger defects. However, the progression of the score is inconsistent. These irregular increments come from the number of honeycomb cells cut and filled inside the radius. Net increase suggests that many new cells have been affected.

Figure 10 : Influence of honeycomb cavity radius

4 DISCUSSION

4.1 Sensibility analysis

The first sensibility analysis demonstrates that insert length has a significant effect where longer insert may offer a better support to the skin. Longer inserts also means that less resin is present in the cavity, therefore total shrinkage is reduced.

Second analysis shows that increasing the skin rigidity has almost no effect on the surface defect. Thin glass fibre sheets have almost no bending stiffness to resist to resin shrinkage. Anyway, sandwich structure skins are not meant to have high bending stiffness. However, honeycomb rigidity has a notable effect as it is the component supporting the bending of the skins. On the other hand, increasing the rigidity of the honeycomb would increase the density of the whole panel.

Regarding the resin properties, there is no doubt that shrinkage has a tremendous effect on the surface quality. The resin Young's modulus also has a significant effect. A low-modulus resin for the same shrinkage will be constrained in a better way by the surrounding components. With its ability to be more stretched, the resin will not pull its neighbour as much as a high-modulus resin.

The last parameter, the cavity radius, has a pretty clear effect. Just like a circular plate supported on its perimeter, submitted to a pressure, as you reduce the radius, the maximal deflection is reduced. The number of honeycomb cells affected must be considered, just as it is discussed in the result section. Higher radius also means a bigger resin volume which can lead to higher exothermal peak (due to curing) creating undesirable curing gradient.

4.2 Assumptions

Many approximations and assumptions were made in order to model the local deformation. It was a challenge to determine which parameters may have an impact on the final output. This section discusses some of parameters that were not taken into account in the model, their potential impact and the possible corrections that can be made to the model.

As far as the resin characterisation is concerned, the kinetic model, resin shrinkage progression and the mechanical properties are crucial for a representative model. However, it is very difficult to capture every property throughout the whole curing. For example, with the current technique, shrinkage cannot

be measured before the gelation of the resin. Mechanical properties near the gelation are also hard to measure because the resin is still liquid. The curing modelling is also complicated by a non-classical behaviour of the resin kinetics. Many experimental observations suggest that two curing mechanisms may be present.

Considering the scale of the analysis, honeycomb geometrical features need to be considered; such as: glued region along L direction and genuine phenolic resin accumulation in corners leading to various wall thickness. On the mechanical side, the rigidity of the Nomex® paper corner folds may influence the honeycomb behaviour. Stability, compression and buckling characteristics would also need to be considered.

When the used panels are cut along their horizontal plane, in a way that both skin are separated, the skin and remaining honeycomb bend. This observation implies that, residual stresses are released leading to surface deflection, especially after drilling of the skin and the honeycomb.

The resin interface with the surrounding honeycomb and skin is difficult to represent in the numerical model. The adhesion quality is in practice affected by unfilled region in the cavity. Due to its high viscosity, the resin has difficulty reaching every recess. Honeycomb fragments left by the drilling stay partially attached to the main structure. Those remains may hamper the resin flow. Moreover, this void phenomenon is neither constant nor predictable. Currently, the whole model cavity is perfectly filled.

The liquid phase of the resin is currently modelled by solid element with very low stiffness. Even if there is almost no fluid motion, this may impede a slight resin shift induced by gradient of curing. There is no slipping between the resin and its adjacent component, this may also limit resin motion and induce stress.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, it was shown by numerical sensitivity analysis that the defect formation was driven by the resin shrinkage. However, it was also pointed out that the severity of the deformation could be influenced by the surrounding elements. Honeycomb higher rigidity and smaller cavity radius effectively reduce the surface defect amplitude. It was also shown that insert length had significant influence. However, the model requires some improvements to be perfectly representative of the reality. A finer modelling of the resin distribution is still needed. Moreover, the general porosity and unfilled honeycomb cells will be implemented. A better representation of surrounding interaction of the honeycomb will also be crucial to develop a more accurate model not only to observe trends but to reproduce defect geometry. In future work, a validation of the model will be made using experimental measurements (optical, profilometer) of sandwich panel's surface. Thus, a valid and reliable model will then be used to explore new configurations where different geometry, properties, curing cycle or additions to the assembly will be simulated.

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